

**Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica:
Impacts on Climate and the Earth System**

Deep and bottom water masses from SAMBA observations

Deliverable D5.4

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1. Publishable summary

In this deliverable, we present an observation-based assessment of deep and bottom water-mass changes in the South Atlantic, from the SAMBA array (34.5S) to the wider basin. Using historical hydrographic observations and gridded products with rigorous validation of the robustness of dataset choices and analysis of the observational uncertainty, we show that all northward deep and abyssal water masses (including Upper Circumpolar Deep Water - UCDW, Lower Circumpolar Deep Water - LCDW, Antarctic Bottom Water - AABW) shows multi-decadal warmed and saltier over the past three decades, with additional changes in their thickness and volume. These results help improve understanding of Southern Ocean–South Atlantic connections, deep-ocean heat transport, and Antarctic climate influencing pathways, while providing open-access data for future research and model development.

Originally, this deliverable was intended to primarily use newly deployed near-bottom MicroCAT datasets from the deepest SAMBA moorings, as described in Deliverable D5.3 (<https://zenodo.org/records/19665538>). However, delays were reported in deploying and recovering part of the mooring array, necessitating a change in scope in D5.3. As a result, deliverable D5.4 has been expanded to analyse changes in deep and bottom-water masses from the SAMBA array to the broader South Atlantic, using a broader observational dataset that integrates both near-bottom measurements and deep-ocean gridded products across the South Atlantic. By extending the analysis from the SAMBA array (34.5°S) to the broader South Atlantic (45°S–0°N), and extending the analysis from near-real-time period in 2025–2026 to the full historical period over the last 30 years (1995–2024), this deliverable can reduce the spatial and knowledge gaps in ocean observations around South Atlantic, integrate advanced basin-scale comprehensive water mass knowledge into ice sheet climate models development, and support multi-national ocean observing initiatives.

2. Work performed and main achievements

2.1 Description of the work performed

2.1.1 Data description

(1) SAMBA-West data

Between 2010 and 2019, the SAMBA-West (the western component of the South Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation Basin-wide Array (SAMBA) in the Vema Chanel) western boundary line near 34.5°S was occupied repeatedly during the SAM cruises (SAM02–SAM18), run mainly on Argentine (Servicio de Hidrografía Naval–supported) vessels such as R/V Puerto Deseado and ARA Austral with NOAA/AOML participation, combining PIES/CPIES servicing and acoustic telemetry with repeat CTD (and sometimes LADCP) hydrographic sections along the mooring line and onto the shelf (Santos et al. 2025). The QC/processing followed standard shipboard CTD workflows. Observations were calibrated using both pre- and post-cruise factory calibrations (SBE 9plus) when available; if not, conductivity sensors were calibrated using salinity samples measured with the Autosal salinometer, standardised with OSIL SSW. When oxygen samples were collected, SBE43 oxygen sensors were calibrated using oxygen samples measured with the Winkler Method. Post-processed QC is also performed manually to remove questionable observations. In

total, 13 repeated cruises (SAM04-SAM18) with temperature and salinity measurements were conducted, yielding 202 collocated temperature and salinity profiles from 2010 to 2019.

(2) SAMBA-East data

The SAMBA-East (the eastern component of SAMBA in the Cape Basin) CTD data are located nominally near 34.5°S between 0°E and the South African continental margin, which is designed to monitor the time-mean and time-varying components of the South Atlantic overturning circulation and associated water-mass variability south of Africa, monitored by the University of Cape Town. In total, 12 repeated cruises (AGU012, ALG221, ALG237, ALG253, ALG265, ALG275, ALG285, ALG291, ALG295, AGU026 and ALG302) with 271 CTD profiles from repeated occupations between September 2013 and October 2024 were collected, including temperature, salinity, conductivity, dissolved oxygen, pressure, depth and potential density, with profiles extending from the near surface to a maximum pressure of about 5500 dbar. All profiles have undergone preliminary quality control, including the removal of obvious outliers and electronic spikes, in accordance with standard UNESCO/TEOS-10 oceanographic processing guidance. However, post-cruise bottle-sample calibrations and sensor-drift corrections had not yet been applied as the provider indicated that expected sensor-drift corrections are very small and unlikely to affect the interpretation of large-scale hydrographic and water-mass analyses. While expected sensor-drift corrections are small, salinity values should be treated with caution.

(3) IAP monthly gridded product with ensemble members

The IAP (Institute of Atmospheric Physics, Chinese Academy of Sciences) monthly global ocean gridded products for temperature (Version 4.2; Cheng et al., 2024) and salinity (Version 2.1; Cheng et al., 2020) at 1°×1° horizontal resolution for the upper 6000 m with 119 standard vertical levels from 1995 to 2024 are used in this delivery. The atlas data is based on quality-controlled and bias-corrected *in-situ* salinity and dissolved oxygen profiles, and subsequently mapped using the peer-reviewed the EnOI ensemble optimal interpolation method to fill the data-gap regions (Cheng et al., 2024). The EnOI uses a dynamic ensemble to generate 30 temperature and 30 salinity realisations, and the spread of these ensemble members represents both instrumental uncertainty and reconstruction uncertainty (sampling and mapping). Most of the historical SAMBA CTD data were used as one of the data sources in generating the IAP monthly gridded product.

In this report, the discussion of the main results is based primarily on the observation products. Uncertainty in observation-based estimates primarily from limitations in data coverage, differences among mapping and interpolation methods (including climatological assumptions), and instrument-related errors such as systematic temperature biases in XBT, MBT, APB, bottle data, dissolved oxygen systematic bias in Bottle and Argo data, as well as imperfect quality control (Tan et al., 2026). To quantify these uncertainties, we used the 30-member IAP temperature and salinity ensembles to generate 900 (30 × 30) unique temperature–salinity realisations via the multiplication principle. For each ensemble pair, neutral density and other derived variables, such as thickness, were calculated, yielding 900 independent representations of the ocean state. From this ensemble, we derived the median estimate and the 95% confidence interval (N=900), defined by the 2.5% and 97.5% quantiles. This approach incorporates instrumental, sampling, and mapping uncertainties, as described in the subsection “Observation-based gridded products”.

2.1.2 Deep and bottom water mass

The deep and bottom layers of the South Atlantic are governed by several Southern Ocean-derived water masses in the northward lower limb of the AMOC: Upper Circumpolar Deep Water (UCDW), Lower Circumpolar Deep Water (LCDW), and Antarctic Bottom Water (AABW). These three waters can propagate northward from their high-latitude origins through the Argentine Basin, the Brazil Basin, and the Cape Basins. Each of these deep- and bottom-water masses represents a distinct physical property, as described below.

(1) UCDW (27.6~27.9 kg/m³)

UCDW enters the South Atlantic sector at 55°S and then propagates northward alongside the Malvinas Current and feeds into the interior South Atlantic gyre. In the South Atlantic, UCDW is located below (denser than) the AAIW and is characterised and tracked by the pronounced local oxygen minimum value, which is regarded as the core UCDW (Manta et al., 2021). When UCDW reaches the SAMBA-West array at 34.5°S, it is located at relatively shallow deep-water depths, occupying the water column with mean pressure of 1550 dbar (Manta et al., 2021). In this region, UCDW exhibits a distinct extreme oxygen minimum layer below 190 $\mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$. In this study, we defined the UCDW as having a neutral density between 27.6 and 27.9 kg m^{-3} following the suggestion by Manta et al. (2021).

(2) LCDW (28.1~28.27 kg/m³)

Above the abyssal AABW and below the NADW, the Lower Circumpolar Deep Water (LCDW) serves as the critical mixing interface connecting the heavily ventilated bottom waters to the shallower, inter-basin masses. It is the blended (dynamical mixing) product of the southward NADW (North Atlantic Deep Water) with the underlying northward AABW. In the Southern Ocean and the South Atlantic, the LCDW is characterised by a local oxygen minimum value. At the SAMBA-West transect (34.5°S), LCDW occupies an expansive vertical layer, spanning depths of roughly 3800 to 4700 meters (with a mean pressure of 4430 dbar) and is characterised by a mean conservative temperature of 1.07 °C and a practical salinity (S_p) of about 34.77 (Manta et al., 2021). The LCDW flows northward into the Argentine and Brazil Basins, mixing with NADW, and finally, the pure LCDW is no longer detectable/observable at the Equator. In this study, we defined the LCDW as having a neutral density between 28.1 and 28.27 kg m^{-3} following the suggestion by Manta et al. (2021).

(3) AABW (>28.27 kg/m³)

The Antarctic Bottom Water (AABW) represents the densest and coldest water mass in the global ocean, occupying the absolute lowermost bathymetric layers of the South Atlantic. AABW is generated in highly localised, geographically restricted regions along the immediate margins of the Antarctic continent and its shelf seas. The Weddell Sea is the dominant source region for the AABW that actively ventilates the South Atlantic. The formation of AABW is driven by extreme, localised ocean-atmosphere-cryosphere interactions during the austral winter. The brine rejection leads to the dense, high-salinity brine that substantially increases the density of the underlying Antarctic Surface Water, triggering deep vertical convection that reaches the shallow continental shelf floor (Basak et al., 2015). This process transforms the surface water into the Dense Shelf Water (DSW). Then, the DSW flows northward and mixes with higher-salinity, warmer water, forming the Weddell Sea Bottom Water (WSBW), and finally becomes the generalised AABW of the South Atlantic during northward mixing propagation (Basak et al., 2015; Manta et al., 2021).

By the time the AABW layer reaches the high-resolution SAMBA-West Array at 34.5°S (i.e., Vema Channel), its properties have diverged significantly from their source values, with warmer and saltier waters than the formation regions and at depths exceeding 3800 meters. As AABW continues its equatorward into the Brazil Basin, it mixes with LCDW and warms to more than 1 °C, making the pure AABW definition increasingly difficult to sustain. When it reaches north of 5°S, the AABW finally mixes with the overlying NADW, and the pure AABW is no longer detectable (Liu and Tanhua, 2021).

Near the SAMBA line, the AABW is mainly detectable in the Argentina Basin, characterised by low temperatures (mean conservative temperature ≈ -0.07 °C) and low practical salinity ($S_p \approx 34.67$) at 4500 dbar (Manta et al., 2021). In this report, we defined the AABW as having a neutral density greater than 28.27 kg m⁻³, following the recommendation of Manta et al. (2021).

2.1.3 Results of the South Atlantic deep and bottom water mass analysis

(1) Robustness of the dataset choice

In this report, the IAP temperature and salinity gridded products (Cheng et al., 2020; Cheng et al., 2024) are used as the primary data source to assess changes in water-mass properties since 1995. Two major advantages of the IAP product are (i) the availability of ensemble-based uncertainty estimates extending back to 1960—information not accessible in other global products such as Ishii or SIO-Argo, and (ii) it is currently the only monthly atlas gridded product that can reach 6000 m which is not available in products such as EN4, etc. (e.g., SIO-Argo can only reach 2000m). However, its performance in water-mass analyses of the South Atlantic deep and bottom waters (below 2000m) remains insufficiently documented. We therefore evaluate the skill of IAP by comparing the temperature and salinity with independent, high-quality in situ observations from SAMBA cruises (SAMBA-West and SAMBA-East), which serve as the benchmark.

Comparison with ship-based CTD data indicates that the IAP can generally capture the core thermohaline structure of deep and bottom water without producing spurious spikes or abrupt shifts (Fig.1 and Fig. 2): most data points from both SAMBA-West and SAMBA-East fall within the IAP 95% uncertainty range. Particularly, the IAP temperature product could accurately capture the decadal increasing trends at 5000m depth (which belongs to the LCDW and AABW depth range; Fig. 1d and Fig. 2d). However, we also noted that there are a few departures, especially in salinity (Fig. 1e-h; Fig. 2e-h), which should be interpreted cautiously in the following reasons: (1) The IAP gridded products are reconstructed from monthly atlases that blend neighbouring observations; transect-scale variability appears smoother relative to individual cruise measurements. (2) Deep-ocean salinity variations are only around 10⁻³ psu, making the signal highly sensitive to instrumental drift, pressure effects, and calibration uncertainty. This is particularly relevant for the SAMBA-East salinity data, which had not yet undergone post-cruise bottle-sample calibration, where conductivity sensors operate under high-pressure and low-temperature conditions. (3) The IAP product may reflect unresolved or insufficient seasonal variability.

Fig. 1: Robustness of dataset choices for estimating the temperature and salinity properties below 2000m by using the IAP monthly grid products and independent cruise observations at the SAMBA west transect (34.5S, 45W-35W): (a-d) Along-track temperature anomaly comparison at 2500m, 3000m, 4000m, and 4500m from 2010-2019. (e-h) are the same as (-d), but for the practical salinity anomaly comparison. Shaded envelopes denote the 95% confidence interval of the IAP estimates, incorporating instrumental, sampling, and mapping uncertainties. The dots in different colours denote the individual SAMBA-West cruises, with the voyage number indicated in panel (a). All the anomalies are relative to 2010-2011.

Fig. 2: The same as Figure 1, but for the comparison by using the IAP monthly grid products and independent cruise observations along the SAMBA East transect (34.5S, 0-15E) at 2500m, 3000m, 3500m, and 5000m from 2013 to 2024. All the anomalies are relative to 2013-2014.

(2) Changes of deep and bottom water mass since the 1995s

- UCDW

Figure 3 shows that the South Atlantic UCDW has not only become warmer and saltier since the mid-1990s, but has also undergone a substantial structural reorganisation involving both vertical thickness changes and lateral redistribution. First, the UCDW has experienced significant concurrent warming and salinisation,

indicating a systematic thermohaline shift (spiciness changes; defined as density-compensated temperature–salinity variations along isopycnals) (Figure 3a-b). The warming signal may partly reflect enhanced Southern Ocean heat uptake and subsequent advection of Southern Ocean–sourced waters into the South Atlantic (Arumí-Planas et al., 2023; Auger et al., 2021). In addition, Agulhas leakage may contribute to the observed warming and salinisation anomalies through the input of Indian Ocean waters and their subsequent isopycnal mixing and redistribution within the upper-to-intermediate South Atlantic (Schmidt et al., 2021; Arumí-Planas et al., 2023). Spatially, the stronger trend occurs along the southwestern boundary and Polar Front regions (Figure 3e-f).

Second, in addition to the spiciness changes, UCDW also experiences a clear structural adjustment related to the vertical shift in ‘heave’ component (defined as the vertical displacement of isopycnal or neutral-density surfaces; Figure 3c-d). Although the basin-mean thickness tends to decrease, the spatial pattern is highly heterogeneous (Figure 3g-h): In the western basin, UCDW thickness decreases while volume increases, implying that the volume change may be driven by horizontal expansion, increased water mass occurrence frequency, or shifts in water-mass boundaries rather than local vertical thickening. This pattern may be due to (i) the compression of the UCDW layer by shifts in adjacent water masses, such as AAIW and NADW, and (ii) a thermohaline reclassification effect whereby long-term warming and salinification bring a larger fraction of the water column within the UCDW property range (i.e., neutral density range). In contrast, the eastern basin shows increases in both thickness and volume, indicating a more direct enhancement of the UCDW layer.

Nevertheless, the thickness trend should be interpreted with caution because of its relatively large uncertainty, especially before 2010 (Figure 3c). As a result, the apparent decreasing thickness before 2010 is not statistically distinguishable from zero because of large observational uncertainty. This reflects the limited spatial coverage during the pre-deep-Argo era.

Fig. 3: Temporal evolution and spatial trends of South Atlantic Upper Circumpolar Deep Water (UCDW; 45°S–0°N), based on the IAP monthly gridded products from 1995–2024. (a–d) Regional-mean time series of UCDW temperature anomaly, practical salinity anomaly, water mass thickness anomaly, and volume. Shading represents the 95% uncertainty range of the IAP ensemble estimates, incorporating instrumental, sampling, and mapping uncertainties. The orange curves show the linear trend of the time series. All anomalies are relative to the 2005–2024 baseline. (e–h) Spatial linear trends (1995–2024) in the temperature, practical salinity, water mass thickness, and volume. Here, black dots indicate the insignificant trends at 95% confidence level (p-value > 0.05).

- LCDW

Figure 4 shows the temporal evolution and spatial trends of LCDW over the past three decades. First, similar with the UCDW, the concurrent increase in LCDW temperature and salinity suggests a spiciness-related change. The spatial pattern, with stronger warming and salinification in the south-western South Atlantic and along parts of the western boundary, suggests that this signal is closely linked to changes in Southern Ocean source waters and their subsequent northward spreading pathways. A plausible mechanism is the increasing transformation from the Antarctic Bottom Water (AABW) to LCDW, in which the AABW has been reported to be warming in the Southern Ocean over the past 40 years based on WOCE-Argo observations (Johnson et al., 2020; Johnson, 2022). As these modified deep waters propagate northward along the western boundary, continued mixing and water-mass transformation can further alter their temperature and salinity, thereby contributing to the observed changes in LCDW spiciness. This interpretation is consistent with previous evidence for sustained heat uptake in the deep and abyssal ocean, as reported by Purkey and Johnson (2010) and Desbruyères et al. (2016).

In contrast to the robust thermohaline trends, changes in LCDW thickness and volume are more spatially heterogeneous and exhibit greater decadal variability. Although the basin-mean thickness and volume both show decreasing tendencies, their spatial patterns may suggest distinct dynamical mechanisms between the western and eastern South Atlantic basins. In the western basin, positive trends in thickness and volume are observed. As LCDW and Weddell Sea AABW spread northward along the western Brazil Basin (Chidichimo et al., 2023), the western-basin thickness and volume increases may reflect an enhanced local presence or accumulation of LCDW associated with the transformation of northward-spreading AABW into the LCDW density/property range. This interpretation is also consistent with the reported contraction of the deepest AABW volume (because the AABW formation rate is decreasing), which may require a compensating thickening of LCDW (Purkey and Johnson, 2012). By contrast, the eastern basin, particularly the Angola Basin, exhibits a pronounced decline in LCDW thickness and volume, possibly reflecting stronger mixing/invasion from the overlying NADW, vertical compression of the LCDW layer, and progressive loss of a distinct LCDW signature under topographic isolation (constrained by the Mid-Atlantic Ridge and Walvis Ridge; Chidichimo et al., 2023). Further work is needed to determine whether these structural changes are primarily controlled by shifts in the upper boundary, or the lower boundary, or both.

In short, the warming and salinization signals of LCDWs have been relatively more confident over the past 30 years, whereas changes in thickness and volume are more complex and uncertain.

Fig. 4: The same as Fig. 3, but for the South Atlantic Lower Circumpolar Deep Water (LCDW; 45°S–0°N).

- AABW

Figure 5 shows the temporal evolution and spatial trends of AABW in the Argentina Basin over the past three decades. First, similar to UCDW and LCDW, AABW in the Argentina Basin also exhibits significant warming and salinification over the past three decades, indicating a spiciness-related thermohaline modification (Figure 5a-b). Spatially, both temperature and salinity increase over much of the AABW-occupied region (Figure 5e-f), suggesting that the thermohaline properties of AABW entering the South Atlantic have undergone systematic changes. However, the abrupt salinity decreases around 2020 might be partly affected by Argo salinity-drift issues in real-time Argo profiles, but still needs further investigation. More broadly, the observed abyssal warming in the Argentina Basin is consistent with recent Deep Argo and repeat-WOCE hydrography studies showing ongoing changes in AABW properties over the past 40 years (Johnson 2022).

Second, the thickness and volume diagnostics further suggest a heave-related structural adjustment of AABW. Both quantities show a weak increasing tendency before ~2018, followed by a rapid decline, implying a thinning and contraction of the water column in recent years (Figure 5c-d). This phenomenon is consistent with reduced formation and export of Weddell Sea-derived dense waters (Zhou et al., 2023; Purkey and Johnson 2012), which can weaken the renewal of AABW entering the South Atlantic abyss. The sharp decrease in volume and thickness after 2018 (Figure 5c-d) may also help explain the concurrent increase in lighter LCDW volume (Figure 4c-d) at the same period, as the overlying LCDW can expand as a compensating lighter deep-water class. One possible mechanism is that AABW warming and mixing during northward spreading shift part of the densest AABW across the AABW–LCDW property boundary, thereby reclassifying it as LCDW. Nevertheless, further diagnostics are needed to determine whether the observed change is primarily controlled by shifts in the upper AABW–LCDW boundary, changes in bottom-water supply, or both.

Overall, the AABW in the Argentina Basin exhibited substantial spiciness changes over the past 30 years, while its thickness and volume generally tended to decrease in the past 10 years, indicating that the AABW is undergoing changes in water mass properties and spatial contraction. This result represents a further step beyond Johnson (2022) and Johnson et al. (2020) by using continuous time series to examine water-mass changes. It further extends these earlier studies by including salinity changes, whereas previous work focused mainly on temperature.

Fig. 5: The same as Fig. 3, but for the South Atlantic Antarctic Bottom Water (AABW; 45°S–0°N). Here, due to the abyssal depth, only the Argentina Basin can detect the AABW in the defined neutral density range.

2.1.4 Deviations from the original plan

The original objective of this deliverable was to focus on abyssal-layer variability along the SAMBA line at 34.5°S, using the newly deployed near-bottom MicroCAT sensors on the eastern and western abyssal plains, as per D5.3. However, as reported in D5.3, the recovery of the SAMBA-East MicroCATs has been postponed to October 2026 following an unforeseen vessel incident, while the SAMBA-West deployment was also delayed until June 2025 due to the cancellation of the originally planned Argentine cruise (S. Speich 2025). As a result, the new near-bottom MicroCAT observations will not be calibrated, validated, and available within the lifetime of the OCEAN ICE project.

To mitigate this delay and ensure that this deliverable still provides a scientifically robust assessment of deep- and bottom-water mass variability, the analysis was redirected toward historical and currently available observational datasets. The geographical scope was therefore expanded from the SAMBA section at 34.5°S to the broader pan-South Atlantic domain (45S–0N), allowing the study to place SAMBA-related variability within a basin-scale context. This revised approach uses historical SAMBA hydrographic data (SAMBA-west and SAMBA-east) together with observational gridded products to examine changes in the deep and bottom South Atlantic water masses over the past 30 years. Accordingly, D5.4 now provides a consolidated analysis of the deep and bottom water masses (LCDW, UCDW, AABW) ranging from the SAMBA array to the broader South Atlantic (45°S–0°N), integrating both the available deep-bottom SAMBA measurements and the expanded deep-ocean gridded products described above.

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2.3 Open Science

The open-access dataset underlying this deliverable is deposited in the Zenodo repository (<https://zenodo.org/records/20268065>) as open access, with tags pointing to OCEAN ICE.

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A scientific output is relevant to D5.4, this is the manuscript entitled "Observed an ongoing 'Indianification' in the South Atlantic intermediate layer over the past 30 years" by Zhetao Tan, Elaine McDonagh, Sabrina Speich, Cristian Florindo Lopez, Mathieu Delteil, Xabier Davila Rodriguez, Laurent Bopp, Emil Jeansson, Tarron Lamont, currently in preparation and plan to submit for peer review before the conclude of the OCEAN ICE project. The authors will select a CC BY licence, and the work will be published in open access with no embargo period.

At the European Geosciences Union General Assembly 2026 (EGU26, Vienna, May 2026), project member Zhetao Tan, lead author of the D5.4 draft, presented the latest findings of observed an ongoing 'Indianification' in the South Atlantic intermediate layer over the past 30 years, using the above-mentioned open-access dataset (<https://meetingorganizer.copernicus.org/EGU26/EGU26-6434.html>).

3. Impact

This deliverable contributes to achieving the following project objectives, as described in the description of the action.

O1: Reduce the spatial and knowledge gaps in ocean observations around Antarctica, particularly relating to ice sheet-ocean interaction and deep water formation and export.

This deliverable supports this specific objective by using direct observations to provide full spatial and temporal coverage of water-mass changes along the northward lower limb of the AMOC in the Antarctica-Atlantic sector. Specifically, it (1) addresses key knowledge gaps in the decadal to multidecadal changes of UCDW and LCDW as they extend northward into the high-latitude Atlantic sector, (2) fills spatial and knowledge gaps in our understanding of abyssal and bottom-water changes through continuous time series, which in the previous studies was only based on specific repeated cruises and individual Argo floats. and (3) identifies potential mechanisms that control their export pathways around Antarctica and links these pathways to their formation regions, such as the Weddell Sea.

O3: Improve representation of AIS dynamics and integrate this knowledge into ice sheet and coupled ice sheet-climate models.

This deliverable contributes to this specific objective by providing observation-based evidence of recent changes in the Circumpolar Deep Water (CDW; including LCDW and UCDW) in the South Atlantic, including trends in temperature, salinity, thickness, and volume. These changes (especially temperature) are important for coupled ice-sheet-climate models because CDW is a major source of ocean heat for Antarctic ice-shelf melting. By extending the analysis from the SAMBA line to the broader South Atlantic, this deliverable provides a broader historical context for CDW variability and can help improve model evaluation of deep-layer ocean heat transport and water-mass transformation. In particular, the deliverable complements and extends earlier observational efforts such as Schmidtko et al. (2014). These results can

also support future studies on the role of anthropogenic warming in CDW changes and their impacts on Antarctic ice shelves.

O7: Deliver free and open access to all data obtained in the project and contribute to international assessments (e.g. IPCC), climate model development, multi-national ocean observing initiatives (e.g. SOOS, All-Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance) and policymakers.

Data consolidation and delivery will be achieved through close integration with SOOS, EMODnet, and Copernicus data delivery services, in accordance with FAIR principles and INSPIRE. The manuscript highlighted in this deliverable will support the upcoming IPCC-AR7 assessment, particularly contributing to WGI Chapter 4 (Advances in process understanding of Earth system changes). The underlying results and corresponding datasets will also support engagement with key international initiatives, including SOOS, SAMOC, and the EU Polar Cluster